

A STUDY ON EXCELLING IN ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILL AND ITS DIFFICULTIES AMONG TERTIARY LEVEL STUDENTS

K.SONIKA¹, Dr.V.MANIMOZHI, Ph.D²

1. Research Scholar, Department of English, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research.

2. Professor & Head, Department of English, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research.

ABSTRACT:

In this generation, English has transfigured as international language which is evolved in business, technologies and academic communication. This drift and craze of English proliferation, as a universal occurrence, makes it requisite to connect with people from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds and in a mixture of settings. Presently, the predominance of English users can be discovered in countries where the language is applied as a foreign or second language. Effectual usage of English as a second language (ESL) or foreign language (EFL) in verbal communication is, undoubtedly, particularly common, but also more intricate and difficult and thus people need to learn and the ability to get along with others in learning the skills. Speaking skill is an essential characteristic to obtain when learning a second or foreign language, and the achievement of learning the language is calculated from the conduct of learners to utter the language learned. Students of English as foreign language (EFL) are insisted to speak English fluently and appropriately by using the target language. The students should be conscious of the competence skills so that they can use the skills as well as they expected to be. English language is a global language as no language is spoken extensively as English Language today. In many countries like Malaysia, India, and Singapore, English language has been exercised as their second language. In Singapore, the citizens speak English language since, among other languages spoken in India like Tamil, Malayalam, and Telugu, English is comprehensively employed as their means of communication. English is contemplated as the foremost language now-a-days. It is also the official language of Pakistan. This research aimed to examine the difficulties of learning English Speaking skills among tertiary level students. Students shared common problems in learning English related to the

issues of vocabulary shortage, grammar difficulties, pronunciation problems, low speaking and listening skills.

Keywords: Influence of the English Language, Students' Difficulties in Speaking English Language, The Strategies to Deal with the Difficulties

INTRODUCTION:

The modern world is a global village and technology seems to grow more and more each day. It expands with every person every touch and every click and we are near the world community. Because communication has become essential in education and students not only prefer to study in their own country but they also try to move abroad. They tend to express themselves by communicating with each other. People around the world can share their thoughts, emotions and ideas through a mutual language. Anyone who knows real good English might be learned by reading books. Begin with comics like Superman, The Dark Knight Returns etc and fairy tale stories like Rapunzel, Alice in the Wonderland, Robinson Crusoe, the wizard of Oz etc - these books create curiosity in one's mind to know what happens next. English is not just about being grammatically perfect but also about how well you frame your words when you communicate with others. Acquiring English knowledge is the process of grasping and accumulating acquired facts in memory. Akram and Qureshi (2012) investigated language and education in English in Bourora and Vehicles. Research concludes that in order to improve the student's pronunciation, the teacher should know his weaknesses and powers about English pronunciation, and he should present himself as a model. However this study is concerned about students learning difficulties and its purpose considers the young learners at the Higher Secondary Level who were not recognized with a learning disability, but still have notable struggles in learning a foreign language, like English. The subject of the study focuses on the analysis of struggles while learning English Language in the classroom. For this purpose, data have been collected through survey method. In the field survey, there were 30 participants, including male & female students. Teachers and students shared various opinions of English language learning difficulties. Most of them responded that students were weak in English Grammar, Vocabulary, and Speaking Skill. After analyzing their English language learning

complexities, the researcher came to conclusion through recommendations and some fruitful steps. In this way, it would like to unveil a new dimension of English language learning for the tertiary Level students in 21st –century. The difficulties experienced by the students’ have made it challenging for teachers in teaching the skills. The challenges that are dealt by the teachers in teaching the skills are complex to persuade their students, students from diverse levels, difficult subject materials and time restraint to teach the students. In order to enhance the student’s learning ability, more consciousness should be given by a teacher to develop the skills of students such as giving guidance and feedback. Therefore, a teacher needs to be aware of the challenges encountered by various English teachers in training the students and ESL students’ challenges. This study gives a detailed explanation on learning difficulties faced by both teachers as well as students in teaching and learning the English language skills.

INFLUENCE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE:

According to Marcell Haller, “How important is it today to speak the English language fluently or at least understand it? It may be one of the most important things when you want to apply for a job. In other words, speaking English is no longer considered as something special, it is a requirement. Nowadays the English language has definitely become a global lingua franca. Speaking English makes it possible to communicate with people all over the world and from many different cultures. As a result English has come to have a large influence on a multitude of other languages, especially in Europe where many words have been adopted outright.” Whereas English has had a immense impact on numerous languages, it has also been considerably influenced by other languages. It is evaluated that over 80% of the English vocabulary has been adopted from further languages. Many of these borrowed words have become so common that we don’t even notice them as foreign any more. For example, money in French it is “monnaie” other words like origin – “origine” ,habit – “habitude” etc nickel – “kupfernickel” from German, armada, cafeteria from Spanish. Languages have never been stable and have always been changing. Over the last few decades, as worldwide has increased and the US has prevailed the world’s most dominant country, the progress of English has conquered a new momentum. Because English is accelerating the currency of the universal, it is intricate to convey any objection. Depending on the centennial languages influenced by Latin or French and as of now we use foreign words without worries that we are desolating our native language. Instead, these words have simply been adopted into our own language. In the end it’s in our hands which words we use from other languages and which ones we continue to use in our native language.

STUDENTS' DIFFICULTIES IN SPEAKING ENGLISH LANGUAGE:

When students converse, they make up ideas in words, convey their notions, their tenderness, and their aims, so that the converser grasp the meaning of what the speakers mean. Language is a very important tool that makes the converser to explain their survival, and for asking something, and to convey the agreement and disagreement. For this reason, oral language or speaking is regarded principle. Achieving fluency in oral communication is the main dream and the main motivation which a large percentage of learners bring to language classes (Richards & Renandya, 2002). There is no denying the role that teachers play in the educational system. He or she is essential to the teaching and learning process, as the effectiveness and competency of the process determine the caliber of education. The success of reforms and the growth of educational programs can be attributed, above all, to the human factor—the teacher. We can all agree that teacher educators are essential to the teacher education program, and that there is a need for many more of them to take on more responsibility and fill a bigger number of new jobs. To ensure that all student teachers and working teachers receive superior training methods, those teacher educators should collaborate across various local, state, and federal organizations. The teacher educator treats the student teachers with equal regard and creates a relationship with them. He / She uses a variety of strategies, such as a positive attitude to inspire student instructors. He also gives them plenty of autonomy within the proper facilities to foster their creativity and allow them to develop naturally during their work experience. The teacher educator elicits several responses from the students through the use of thought-provoking questions, demonstrating their excellent imagination and breadth of knowledge. There is a paucity of excellent English teacher. Teaching has always been the contests part for teachers. Teaching English at primary level is generally varies from teaching in other category of students such as secondary and tertiary levels. The complexities will somehow make the teachers' teaching worthless. Having such various category of students in the classroom is another different difficulty handled by teachers in explaining the classes. Various levels of learning abilities requires the teachers to use varied approaches. Hence it makes the teachers to feel tough in planning their lessons and complexity in preparing appropriate activities and tasks for the students. If teachers are not familiar with English language, it is impossible for

the students to crack the interviews ,to get into a job or to study abroad. If this situation is continued, Higher Secondary Level learners fail to learn English properly. There is no English Language lab. Generally, we know that there is no other way without English Language lab if any student dreams to speak, write, or read. He must go to the English lab; his/her academic learning is insufficient since teacher are not well-trained and expert. To excel inEnglish, it plays a vital role for the students' and it is useful to practice the four skills of Englishlanguage. In the 21st -century, if we take a look at primary, secondary and higher secondary level institutions in Tamilnadu in few schools and colleges, we could find out that teachers take classes without multimedia projectors. Since students don't receive multimedia project learning in the field of education system, the concerned authority should ensure the very fact so that multimedia projector can be established in all classes to develop education policy. Numerous students fear that they come up with so many ideas in their minds, but when it comes to conversation, they have no notion at all about what has to be said. Few pupil say that they are not confident with their grammar, afraid of being criticized, lack of vocabularies, nervous, worry, and anxious. However, foreign language learners experience frustrating feeling of not being able to participate in speaking activity. Most EFL learners and perhaps some of the teachers believe that oral communication problems can be solved through more practices in vocabulary and structure, learning and using language in a foreign context is strongly connected to the learner's constructions of self (Arnold, 2000). In fact, achieving fluency in speaking is not easy. Students are not only demanded to use grammar correctly or having good pronunciation and vocabulary, they are also demanded to know the knowledge of how to use the language. Hinkel (2005) claims, communication problems occur because the learner encounter a word they do not understand, a form of word they do not know how to use, or find that they are unable to express their intended meaning. Parental indifference is another challenge. Lack of parents' support will make the teachers having a hard time to help the students. Students who feel lack of warmth and affection from their parents will draw them back from succeeding in their learning process(Gündoğmuş, 2018). Other problems that appear in student's speaking are lack of self confident and anxiety. They may confront with certain feelings that affect their English speaking such as unconfident, shy, anxious, nervous, and worry. If the students themselves are not believing that they are able to speak, it has become a big problem for them.

THE STRATEGIES TO DEAL WITH THE DIFFICULTIES:

The strategies to deal with the difficulties that were implemented to the students were reading online comic, learning vocabulary, reading English article or essays, listening to short stories, telling a story using English language and increasing confidence. English activity programs, doing English exercises, getting used to the English language, and using the correct English language will enable the students to acquire knowledge and can master the speaking skill. To provide the learners' maximum benefit and to make the class effective and enjoyable, teachers should involve the students in a variety of activities, such as Hello English app, Kahoot app, group work, pair work, role play, question-answer, discussion, debating, realia, etc. Textbook should be followed strictly. Classes should be participatory and teacher-student-oriented. Tasks should be interesting and relevant to the learners' life and environment. All four basic skills of English language would be practised in the classrooms in an integrated manner, not in isolation. Grammar would be taught through the communicative approaches. Some language games, puzzles, and jokes may be used as exercises for developing students' English Speaking skill through fun and entertainment. In every class, new vocabulary should be introduced. Furthermore, in teaching and learning English for work-related purposes, emphasis should be placed on teaching technical and business communication as well as technology-assisted language learning. In order to accomplish the course's goals and objectives, the assignments and activities should be created with the needs of the students in mind.

KEY STRATEGIES:

The academic achievement of English language learners needs current updating and co-construction among teachers, schools, parents, families and communities. It has five key strategies to meet the project goals:

- Training for Teachers – to prepare teachers to improve content area instruction for students and the training has to cope up the teachers which should be helpful to them as well as the students.
- Technical Assistance for Classroom Support – a support system for preparing the content by using online tools in explaining and projectors should be made possible.
- Teacher Mentoring – a support system for mentoring beginning and experienced

teachers in making the studies easier for students by instructing and appropriate trainings to students.

- Teacher-Parent Partnerships – a system to bring parents and educators together for planning and in helping the students to overcome the barriers and guiding them to achieve their goals.
- ESL Learning – a sustainable collaborative structure for ESL teachers, content area teachers and administrators to monitor and support the progress of students by making learning complexities easier.
- Students should be given many opportunities to improve their vocabulary.
- It is recommended that teaching methods be revised and updated, with a focus on communicative and objective-based tactics, rather than exam-oriented ones.
- It would be beneficial to adapt language learning methodologies, as well as testing and assessment techniques, in order to reflect cognitive learning styles.

CONCLUSION:

Thus the study focuses on the learning process and teaching methods that could be applied to minimize learning difficulties of young learners at tertiary level in Vellore district who were not assessed with a learning intricacy, but still have remarkable problems in learning a foreign language, like English. The aim of the paper is ‘to use multiple methods which would develop and motivate the young learners to learn English as a foreign language with less complexities’, the beginning stage starts from the hypothesis that the same teaching methods used with learning- disabled students could be trained to support students with learning disabilities and help them to master the speaking skill of English from the start of their studies. Children improve their strategies like imitation, repetition and formulaic speech which help them to acquire their mother tongue; and hence the beginners also come across the same kind of process while learning a foreign language. However neither children nor beginners might do this alone, and remarkably their parents and teachers have to take part in this process to lead them to success. Besides strategies, there are other instruments that facilitate acquisition of a foreign language. Each student may face different challenges during this learning stage. Every student is special and unique in their own ways of learning. These difficulties will somehow make the students to improve and to move forward to excel in learning the second language. To be concluded teachers have to be trained as well as students in order to make the learning atmosphere easier. Language labs, projectors, online

access for teachers to prepare the learning materials and time to prepare the syllabus before handling the classes. Teachers have to be aware of handling different kind of students and it needs various approaches, methods and techniques to be followed while teaching. Besides the management and institutions must take necessary steps in order to facilitate the teachers to have effective teaching process and to make the learning atmosphere easier for the students.

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